

C O U N C I L O N L I B R A R Y R E S O U R C E S

A REVIEW OF ITS WORK

Foreword	
National Library Services	1
Automation and Networks	19
Preservation and Care of the Collection	35
Microforms, Reprography, Nonprint Media	39
Technical Aids	51
Administration and Management	56
The Interface: Libraries and Their Users	64
International Activities	79
The Profession	86

FOREWORD

No resource is more important than the library in the preservation of man's culture and in his quest for knowledge. Yet in the 1950s -- when libraries were desperately struggling to deal with the problems that resulted from efforts to meet the needs of increasing numbers of patrons working in fields where recorded knowledge was growing at an exponential rate -- there was little outside help available to them. It is true that some foundation funds were being channeled into libraries, but these were generally earmarked for the erection of buildings and the improvement of collections and thus failed to attack major sources of difficulty. Confronted with rising costs, staff shortages, outdated buildings and procedures, libraries were falling far short of their own goals as well as the expectations of their users.

In order to discover the most useful kind of help it could provide in this situation, the Ford Foundation in 1954 began an inquiry into the needs of libraries and the relation of those needs to society. The inquiry culminated in two day-long meetings at the Folger Shakespeare Library, when some fifty librarians, scholars, and university administrators considered the problems of libraries and the means for solving them.

On the basis of the recommendations of the Folger group as well as its own investigation, the Foundation concluded that it could best help libraries through the establishment of an independent organization under distinguished leadership, prepared to address itself exclusively to the problems over a suitably long period of time, free to range widely through research and development in all fields to determine new attacks upon the traditional

problems, and to accelerate library development by encouraging new methods and helping to coordinate their application.

Accordingly, in 1956 the Foundation established the Council on Library Resources "for the purpose of aiding in the solution of the problems of libraries generally and of research libraries in particular, conducting research in, developing and demonstrating new techniques and methods, and disseminating through any medium the results thereof, and for making grants to other institutions and persons for such purposes; and for providing leadership, and wherever appropriate, coordination of efforts (1) to develop the resources and services of libraries and (2) to improve relations between American and foreign libraries and archives."

From the outset it was apparent that no organization, no matter how great its resources, could even begin to eliminate the many inadequacies of individual libraries. And so it became the Council's policy to provide support only for programs that might contribute to the solution of library problems in general rather than in particularized or local terms. It was -- and still is -- equally obvious that not all issues could be attacked simultaneously, that the Council would have to develop a kind of priority listing of target areas in order to deal with first things first. These areas have of course changed as the needs and technologies have changed, and the early concentration on development of technical aids has given way to the present emphasis on encouragement of service at the national level, management, personnel development, and application of the new technology.

In the 17 years since 1956 -- a period during which annual library and information costs (exclusive of buildings) increased from the millions to the billions -- the Council has spent approximately \$19,500,000 of the

just over \$21,000,000 thus far received from the Foundation on projects, fellowships, and self-administered programs designed to carry out the charge laid upon it at its establishment. How well it has accomplished its mission can best be judged by others. It is hoped that this paper will afford a point of departure.

June 30, 1973

NATIONAL LIBRARY SERVICES*

The United States, unlike some other countries, has no national bibliographic center as such. The Library of Congress (LC) performs many of the bibliographic services required by the country's libraries, but it is by statute the congressional library and its first obligation is meeting the needs of the Congress. The National Library of Medicine and the National Agricultural Library also provide services to libraries in their respective fields. However, there is no official attempt effectively to coordinate these efforts and others that are going forward on a private level, or to carry out a systematic, centralized assessment of their shortfalls against the total requirement. What is needed is an agency with the authority to develop coherent plans for the elimination of these shortcomings and the stature then to command funds for the execution of those plans. Conceivably, the relatively new National Commission for Libraries and Information Science may ultimately provide the required leadership, but it is unlikely that this will happen soon. In the present absence of official national guidance, the Council will continue to encourage cooperative efforts by the three national libraries as well as compatibility and standardization among individual libraries and regional centers moving toward automation.

In an ideal situation, the United States would, perhaps, have a single library system wherein the optimum degree of centralization would ensure the best of resources to provide the best possible services to library clientele. Cataloging would be done once, at the center, and centralized procurement

*By "National Library Services" is meant services available to all libraries in the country and provided by central sources, whether governmental or private.

would serve the acquisitions requirements of all libraries. The economies thus gained would permit cataloging, and especially indexing, in greater depth, as well as the improvement of other services. Cataloging data would be available on demand and would reach using libraries in a timely manner, as would books and other materials centrally procured for them.

There would be a single national data base in machine-readable form encompassing all types of literature. It would be based on the combined holdings of the three national libraries and could include also the additional holdings of other libraries. This would require that the central bibliographic services of the three national libraries be fully automated and completely compatible with each other. A communication network would make the combined assets of the national system freely available to all libraries and, through them, to their users.

To build a system of this sort would take years and funds that are, for libraries, enormous. Very large sums of money are obviously not now available for the purpose, and even if they were, a single system of the type described probably could not now be built. For one thing, such a system is not politically feasible in this country. Our library systems are so diverse as to mission, lines of responsibility, sources of fundings, etc., as to preclude it. But the systems can continue to cooperate, and that cooperation can be enhanced by the proper application of technology and the concomitant elimination of some wasteful duplication.

What is possible is something like this: A national data base can be built. The use of the literature represented in the data base can be facilitated by the construction of varying arrays of library cooperatives, developing on different schedules, with greatly dissimilar budgets, with their

funding coming from various sources - federal, state, local, and private. What would emerge would be a flexible confederation of library systems working toward an optimum system but basing their plans and expectations on current reality.

It is the Council's policy to select for support those projects which complement each other in our perception of the evolution toward a national system of library service. CLR also continues to encourage the Library of Congress -- which is an essential piece of the whole -- to move in the direction of this same national library system.

At the end of fiscal 1972 the Library of Congress held 85,200,777 pieces of library material, over 21 million of which had been acquired during that year.* Included were books, serials, music, manuscripts, maps, audio and video tapes, phonograph records, photographs, paintings -- in short, items of every medium in which knowledge is recorded. Many of these same pieces were also processed into the thousands of other libraries in this country. Each library required information about these items which would permit their selection, acquisition, cataloging, storage, advertising, retrieval, circulation, and control.

For the purpose of their handling in libraries, materials may be separated into three broad categories, each having subdivisions which impose varying requirements on the library:

- * Monographs (or books)
- * Serials (or periodicals)
- * Nonbook materials

Monographs and serials are cataloged and then segregated into subject classes for shelving. Ideally, each article in the serial issue should itself be con-

*Includes 19,115,050 pieces from Look magazine pictorial file.

trolled as a separate item, but in only a few libraries is this done -- e.g., at the National Library of Medicine and the National Agricultural Library. Nonbook materials are cataloged as individual items in a manner roughly similar to that used for monographs. The catalog entry thus becomes a surrogate which describes a particular package of recorded knowledge.

Cataloging rules have undergone major revision twice in the last 25 years and another revision is in process. The rules are detailed and quite complicated. In spite of many determined efforts to standardize* cataloging and eliminate duplication of effort, the general tendency is for each library to catalog its own books on the basis of its own interpretation of the cataloging rules. (It is expected that Cataloging in Publication (CIP), discussed later in this section, will be significant in the eventual acceptance of standardized cataloging.) Some standards are slowly being introduced, but they must compete in a world where, by tradition, every librarian is largely autonomous.

The improvement of libraries by the application of technology must be approached with a clear understanding of the diversity which exists among American libraries. Some of these differences will be eliminated in time by standardization, centralized cataloging, and centralized data conversion. Others, however, will always be with us and must be allowed for in systems design.

*Traditionally it has been necessary for libraries to have standardized procedures and techniques, if only for internal and individual purposes. With the general move toward cooperation, it has become more and more necessary for standards to be accepted by libraries that wish to utilize one another's resources. As it has become clear that libraries are dependent upon one another not only nationally but internationally, it has been increasingly essential to develop standards that are universally acceptable. Particularly as computers have come to be an aspect of library work, exact and completely standardized records have become a vital necessity. "Standards" and "strandardization" as used in this paper refer to the above description -- that is, primarily standardization of records.

Data Base Development

One phenomenon associated with decentralized and uncoordinated library development is the simultaneous evolvment in many places of machine-readable bases of bibliographic data. The fact that such data bases are now being developed in various places throughout the country clearly establishes the widespread requirement for them. As they are produced in parallel, many costs are duplicated. Since data base construction is one of the most significant costs of library automation, it is evident that a coordinated national approach to their development is essential.

To be useful and used, a national data base should have a minimum set of attributes: comprehensiveness, authority, accessibility, timeliness, standardization, and reasonable cost. Each of these minimum attributes imposes design parameters on a national data base.

Comprehensiveness - The national data base requirement encompasses all recorded knowledge represented in bibliographic files which are to be handled in automated library systems: monographs, serials, maps, music, audiovisuals, and other nonbook materials.

Authority - To build authoritative data bases requires centralized control. Work may be decentralized, but a single decision-making authority is essential.

Accessibility - To be easily and quickly accessible, the national data base must be in machine-readable form. Products in other forms (i.e., catalogs and special bibliographies) are readily made and disseminated from a machine-readable store.

Timeliness - A data base must arrive in the using library before the start of the library process it is designed to support. This implies differing arrival-time requirements to support selection and ordering, for example, as compared to the requirements for catalog-card production.

Standardization - The standards referred to are bibliographic, those of automatic data processing, communications standards, and some codes and standards which may come from outside the library community, for instance geographical place name codes from the Bureau of Standards. Effective national interchange of data is not possible without widespread compatibility among systems, and to achieve this a much better unified approach to standards than now exists is required. Librarians are coming to the realization that complete autonomy in decision making at the operational level and efficient automation are so inherently incompatible as to be mutually exclusive. The efficiency of automation in libraries varies directly with the acceptance of standards. Standardization requires compromise and, in data base building, it implies centralized authority. (In this context "authority" means the systematic handling of authors' names, including all pseudonyms and variant forms of the name.)

Reasonable cost - It costs several dollars to convert one bibliographic record to machine-readable form and a larger amount to catalog the item recorded. When we consider the tens of millions of records involved, logic would indicate that we should pay this price only once, if this is at all possible.

Discussed below are some extremely significant beginning -- but only beginning -- steps which have been taken toward creation of this essential national data base. The first were, properly, at the Library of Congress, with initiation and considerable assistance from the Council.

The Machine-Readable Cataloging (MARC) Project MARC is the result of a series of Council grants to the Library of Congress. It began as a standard format on magnetic tape for the communication to other libraries of bibliographic data concerning monograph titles cataloged at the Library of Congress. MARC was the first development of its kind and magnitude in the world. Because it did not -- and properly could not be expected to -- cover the entire

cataloging effort at LC initially, MARC had to plan to coexist with the balance of that system for years. And the system at LC was geared to the production and filing of catalog cards. Thus, the principal parameters of the MARC design were preordained: it was to be oriented toward catalog cards and the rules for manually filing those cards. There is nothing wrong with these decisions; they were inevitable under the circumstances. But they must be kept firmly in mind when MARC is used, especially when it is used for other than the purpose for which it was designed: the transmission of bibliographic data on magnetic tape. This epitomizes the classic dilemma faced by the librarian when he is forced by circumstances (economic and otherwise) to automate only a part of his library processes. Because so many of the processes will still be done manually, the design of the new system is largely dictated by the old. The filing of bibliographic records offers a case in point.

Bibliographic records are customarily kept on cards, and the number of cards held in a library may range from several thousand to the over 50 million at the Library of Congress. In order for a given card to be retrievable from the mass, some very intricate filing rules had to be devised. But the rules devised for manual filing are not the same rules the computer uses to put records in order. In all library automation projects so far, the filing sequences of the computer have been "bent" to accommodate manual filing procedures, to some detriment to the full potential of the computer. Only when all the library and systems processes which are capable of being handled by computer are so handled will the full benefit of computer use be realized.

External to the Library of Congress, MARC is potentially a great boon to libraries, comparable to the advent of the LC card distribution service, for records in machine-readable form can be manipulated at will. Further, catalog cards are only one type of output possible from them; they also may be used as

machine-readable input to regional or local systems to supplement the local cataloging work. MARC records are already being used in several systems in this way. It should be kept in mind, however, that most libraries will not in the foreseeable future be able to afford to manipulate and utilize the MARC data bases on an individual basis. Consortia of some kind are required, except in the rare instances where a library is large enough and rich enough to go it alone.

RETrospective CONVersion of Catalog Records (RECON) It is evident that if the Library of Congress is not indefinitely to operate two systems, one manual and one automated, covering the same bibliographic records, a complete machine-readable data base is required. Further, as regional and other systems develop across the country, the need for the full data base grows apace. But since the date of its inception MARC has covered only English language monographs cataloged at the Library after that date. Thus it was important to learn something about the feasibility and costs of putting into machine-readable form records on titles in other languages and on English titles already in the file when MARC began. Accordingly RECON, a pilot project to convert retrospective records to MARC, was begun at the Library in 1969 with financial support from the Council, augmented by LC funds and a grant from the Office of Education.

RECON demonstrated the technical feasibility and established the unit costs of various approaches to a full-scale retrospective conversion project at the Library of Congress. After the pilot project ended, the Library of Congress -- for reasons which have not been satisfactorily made clear to the rest of the library community -- elected not to seek a congressional appropriation for further work on the program. It should be said that the costs of such a conversion at the Library are far beyond the capacity of a private

group to bear. As a result some libraries and commercial houses around the country are, generally individually and without reference to the need for compatibility among them, working to convert their own much smaller retrospective data bases to MARC form.

The National Serials Program Serials are those items of literature which are published on a regular, continuing basis in numbered volumes and issues. Recent studies and pilot work by the three national libraries have clearly established the requirement for a coordinated national approach to the control of serial literature. This approach must accommodate all producers, handlers, and users of serials -- publishers, libraries, indexing and abstracting services, researchers, other readers, and the general public.

The world population of serials is variously estimated at 600,000 to 750,000 titles, with perhaps half that number currently in publication. The serial record at LC contains approximately 1,300,000 catalog cards. A problem of such magnitude is best approached in phases, and Phase I began at the Library of Congress in 1967, funded in part by the Council.

In Phase I the serials universe was studied and the library community questioned about definitions, purposes, and what should be included in a serial record. Predictably, this resulted in a mass of data about serials. Thus approached, the serials problem appeared too massive for solution. It was therefore decided to mount a small pilot effort outside the Library of Congress that would be separate at first from the internal serials processing there. The Association of Research Libraries was designated executive agent for the pilot project, under the aegis of the National Libraries Task Force, which included on its staff two Council employees. The prime purpose of the project was to experiment with machine-readable bibliographic data on selected serials held by the three national libraries, in order to learn as much

as possible, to build files, and to establish techniques and procedures upon which a National Serials Program could later be built.

With the assistance of the Council, which contributed not only funds but the nearly full-time work of one of its systems specialists, the Pilot Project was successfully concluded. A Council staff member drew up a plan based on the project's findings for the next phase, the follow-on National Serials Data Program (NSDP). The plan was accepted by the heads of the three national libraries and the program established as a separate entity within the Library of Congress in 1972. In its first year, operational funds were supplied almost equally by the three national libraries and the Council. The Council also furnished one full-time systems specialist and one program officer part time to assist the NSDP. CLR provided this concentrated assistance because a national program of this type is critically needed by all the libraries in the United States. Further, it was felt that its participation might serve to move the Library of Congress from its position of apparent reluctance to give the program the degree of support it requires. It now appears that, although the other partners in NSDP are ready to go on with and even to enlarge the scope of the program, the Library of Congress may not find it possible to continue its funding, even at the initial level. (This is subject to change; it is possible that designated funds deleted from the LC budget by the House Committee will be restored by the Senate.) Suspension of the program would be most unfortunate, for as the successful work of NSDP has gained visibility and understanding among librarians and other users of serials, there has been growing demand for its faster development so that its products and services can be utilized by local systems. The United Kingdom, Germany, Russia, and Australia have announced the activation of their own national serials systems; France and the Scandinavian countries are next. And the capping International Serials Data System (ISDS) is operational in Paris. The

American part of the system must not be allowed to bog down, and the Council will continue to work toward its further implementation.

Standard Serial Numbers -- National and International

Serials systems require that each title be uniquely identified. If the handling of titles is to be automated, the requirement for unambiguous title identification is absolute. Serials titles frequently change, and computers are quite unable to make the subjective decisions that are then required about the relationship between dissimilar titles for the same serial. Look-up tables can be constructed which will allow the computer logically to decide that the one equals the other, but to include all possibilities (some unforeseeable) requires immense computer storage and an extravagant amount of computer time. This can be avoided if each serial title always bears a unique number, no matter what the form of catalog entry.

In the United States, Committee Z39 of the American National Standards Institute (ANSI) is the group charged with formulating and gaining acceptance of standards needed in library work, documentation, and related publishing activities. Z39 receives its support from the Council and the National Science Foundation. Council staff members serve on various of its subcommittees, including the one responsible for developing the U.S. standard for serial numbers (SSN), which was promulgated and accepted in 1970.

Standardization within the United States, however, was only the first step toward achieving final clarity. Today scholars of every discipline depend, for current information in their fields, on journals issued in a variety of languages by publishers all over the world. Thus the problem remains unresolved unless there exists a universally accepted standard for identifying serials, no matter what their country of origin. The International

Standards Organization (ISO), of which ANSI is a component, is the body responsible for adopting such a standard; it has this year circulated to its constituent members for final balloting a proposed International Standard Serial Number (ISSN) based on Z39's SSN and meeting all U. S. requirements. Here too CLR staff participation, this time in the work of ISO Technical Committee 46, was an important factor as the international library community made an essential move in an unbelievably complex situation.

While the work on the standard itself was going on, the Council was already looking to the future and taking steps to see to it that when the ISSN was officially adopted the United States would be ready to begin its application to a large body of serials. This required, among other things, obtaining agreement on a number of important questions from representatives of other countries, and the U. S. point of view was successfully represented by a CLR staff member who acted as a technical consultant during the development of the International Serials Data System (ISDS), the group charged with the assignment of ISSNs to the national centers for local application. The Council performed useful behind-the-scenes work in developing the plan for the designation of the U. S. Center, the first thus established.

In very much the same sort of way, the Council played an important part in gaining acceptance of the MARC serials format internationally and in influencing the development of the International Standard Serials Description so that it is compatible with the ISSN and with the serial record of the U. S. national program.

The activities here recounted are significant not only for their value to the serials program but also as an example of how the Council serves the national and international library community in a capacity well beyond that of grant-making and -monitoring. Because its only purpose is to aid libraries,

because it has the ability to react quickly and effectively to needs as they emerge, and because it has on its staff "experts in residence" whose guidance is known to be informed and nonself-serving, the Council can influence developments in a way that cannot be accomplished by any other library group, private or public.

Cataloging in Publication (CIP)

Not all the work the Council has done in the area of National Library Services is based on automation. Perhaps one of the most important programs falling in this category is Cataloging in Publication.

Access to the library holdings is through the catalog, usually a card catalog, which in any of its forms lists publications generally by author, title, and subject. Maintenance of these catalogs in the United States depends largely on basic catalog cards prepared by the Library of Congress and made available to all libraries wishing to purchase them. This system, which has operated for 70 years, not only contributes to standardization in cataloging but also provides great savings of time and money to U.S. libraries.

For some of those 70 years various librarians had felt that the system could be improved by having the cataloging information available in the book itself instead of on a separate card. Such a system would eliminate a noticeable time lag in receiving the information needed before a book can be made available to the user and would also lower appreciably the costs for libraries. Under the system it would no longer be necessary to order cards individually, await shipment, check their receipt, compare with the book to assure identity, and prepare payment.

Cataloging in Publication, which provides official LC cataloging in the book itself, exists today as a result of Council initiative, stimulation, guidance, and support. A preliminary experiment, supported by CLR, was carried out by the Library of Congress and U.S. publishers in 1958-59. Unfortunately the experiment was not adequately evaluated and LC decided not to continue the program. Ten years later however, the time lag in providing cataloging information, the growing number of books which required cataloging by LC, and the enormous increase in orders from libraries for the LC catalog cards created a condition which compelled the reevaluation of Cataloging in Publication. In response to requests from publishers, libraries, and the Librarian of Congress, CLR provided support in 1971 for a renewal of CIP. The Council was successful in enlisting matching funds from the National Endowment for the Humanities, and together the two organizations provided a two-year grant, with the understanding that the work would be continued thereafter as a regular part of the Library's program.

There are presently over 400 publishers participating in the Program. As of May 1973 over 17,000 titles had been processed since the beginning of the Program in July 1971, including 850 titles cooperatively cataloged by LC and the National Library of Medicine. Weekly receipts are currently averaging about 300 titles, representing approximately 55 percent of the U.S. book trade production. The recent addition of many of the larger publishers should increase this figure to approximately 75 percent. Preliminary planning is underway to expand CIP to include selected Federal Government documents. Selection would be based on the objective of covering the material that is

widely acquired and cataloged by libraries. It would begin agency by agency and title by title, without diminishing the continuing emphasis on phasing-in the remaining trade book publishers.

The House Appropriations Committee has approved the Library's \$81.7 million fiscal 1974 request which includes funds for 29 new and permanent positions for CIP. Cataloging in Publication is moving rapidly from its "tryout" status into a fully funded Library of Congress operation.

From the foregoing, several conclusions may be drawn concerning national library services in the United States. First, there is insufficient official guidance for library systems development provided at the national level. The National Commission will eventually provide at least some of this direction, but in its present absence the Council is in a unique position to assist.

The country has a valid requirement for a National Bibliographic Center to provide better national library services while eliminating useless duplication of effort. Some of the services required of such a national center are now being supplied by the Library of Congress (e.g. MARC records, catalog cards, the National Union Catalog, all based on LC's centralized cataloging services); others are being provided, in largely uncoordinated efforts, by individual libraries and library consortia (e.g., the creation, in machine-readable form, of retrospective bibliographic records and prospective records not within the scope of MARC). What is needed to solve these data base and other problems is a national bibliographic service center analogous to the new British Library concept now being implemented in England. Such a center will probably not be established here unless and until there is a major shift in the thinking on the subject in the Congress and in the Library of Congress. Perhaps the best way for the Council to begin its assistance would be through

funding independent study in some depth. Those who conduct the study will need detailed knowledge of LC operations and a large measure of objectivity, a scarce combination of attributes.

As an adjunct to the National Bibliographic Center, a comprehensive national bibliographic data base is required. This is a principal function of any fully operational center. The RECON project referred to earlier in this section proved the technical feasibility of centralized retrospective conversion and showed how much it would cost per record. Unfortunately, the Library of Congress did not follow up with a project for large-scale conversion, and, at this writing, does not seem likely to. In the meanwhile, there is an urgent requirement for someone to coordinate the data base building already going on outside LC in order to eliminate waste and ensure compatibility. Thus the Council, in a series of meetings which began in 1972, is attempting to forge agreements (among those libraries and consortia in good position to contribute to the national data base) as to minimum standards of cataloging, completeness of data records, and data conversion which should be met. The Council is also fostering the idea that agreement to adhere to such standards should be prerequisite to joining library consortia. Efforts in this area have been well received so far.

Perhaps the area most critically deficient in national guidance is the construction of regional library consortia and other library systems, which has already begun. For example, at least nine regions are in various stages of active planning to replicate the system of the Ohio College Library Center (OCLC), which is described in the section on Automation and Networks. Several large libraries (E.G. Stanford, University of Chicago) are building

systems. Still others (e.g. Harvard, Yale, New York Public Library, and Columbia) are banding together into yet-to-be-defined cooperative arrangements. The Council is working with all of these to enhance compatibility and resource sharing among them by funding some of the activities and advising on others. This whole area is in urgent need of national guidance, for example in coordinating the development and use of computer software packages. Uncoordinated projects in software development can easily waste millions. Again, the Library of Congress, with one or two exceptions, has exerted virtually no influence in this vital area, and so the Council has acted to fill, partially at least, the vacuum. Much of the software (the essential logic) needs to be developed only once and coded only once for each family of computers on which it is to be used. Thus a requirement exists for centralized development of this software, availability of training in its use, its documentation, and in technical support when the inevitable systems problems arise. The Council has made a modest beginning in this area. It is funding software development at OCLC, Chicago, Stanford and a few other places. The results of these developments are made widely available, but limitations on Council resources preclude doing all that is required. Here, as with development of a national bibliographic service center, it would be useful to commission a detailed study into the overall requirements and, based on its results, make recommendations for action.

After the studies on the National Bibliographic Center and software support are under way, a logical next step would be to study the proper distribution of products and services from the national center to the field, and the reverse of this flow: how should the nation's libraries and systems contribute to the national effort in the age of library automation and networks?

It is emphasized that there are two separate but intimately related areas urgently requiring action: first, a comprehensive study must be mounted on the requirement for a National Bibliographic Center; this must be followed by a plan which will achieve the solution to these requirements. Even more urgently required is positive action to provide compatibility and resource sharing among the systems already in various stages of development. Obviously, there is a vital connection between the two; the present systems development must fit into the eventual national plan. To date, the Council is in effect the only agency actually working and planning for the coordination of these efforts at the national level.

AUTOMATION AND NETWORKS

Almost from its inception the Council on Library Resources has supported the application of the computer and related technology to library processes. The first project thus undertaken was in 1958, when a grant was made to the National Library of Medicine for the improvement of its Current List of Medical Literature, then the world's largest service, in terms of quantity of material indexed, for the literature of a special subject. The project eventually resulted in MEDLARS (Medical Literature Analysis and Retrieval System), one of the best known computer-supported systems of the present day. Within the past two years the MEDLARS file, which consists of citations to many thousands of articles from current medical literature, has been made available on-line to medical researchers all across the country.

In the six years that followed that first award the Council made grants of close to a million dollars for programs that ranged the field of computerization in libraries as it then existed. Support was given to projects in automatic indexing, searching law by computer, experimental application to the maintenance of serial records, research into the library of the future, computer-controlled typographic composition, optical scanning, and many others... all important and necessary activities in the effort to promote a coordinated approach to the application of automation to library processes. But the real breakthrough came with MARC (Machine Readable Cataloging), developed at the Library of Congress with Council initiative and assistance.

MARC provided what had heretofore been lacking, a standardized format for the transmission of bibliographic data. MARC was, and is, a powerful standardizing influence in the handling of bibliographic records in machine-readable form. Without it, or something like it, the interchange of bibliographic data

or the construction of library networks would be impossible. MARC is quite simply a detailed record layout designed to accommodate all the peculiarities inherent in bibliographic records and to facilitate the end uses to which they are put. Each data element is tagged with a numerical designator; 245 is the tag for title, for example. Since MARC is the American National Standard for the transmission of bibliographic data on magnetic tape, all any automated library system need do is program its computer to recognize as title the character string which follows tag 245; thus quite dissimilar computer systems can exchange bibliographic data among themselves.

MARC is equally significant in library development outside the United States. The MARC scheme is being implemented in Canada, in Europe, and elsewhere around the world; it is also beginning to be accepted as the standard for international exchange of bibliographic information. Thus one can see the early signs of international compatibility among automated library systems. Of course, acceptance of a standard record format affects only some of the mechanical aspects of automated bibliographic data handling; the standardization of the intellectual input to these records is a much more difficult process since traditions and work habits of many years' standing are involved. But MARC is an important beginning.

In the last five years the Council has greatly increased its rate of spending in this area, devoting approximately one-third of its program budget to projects in automation. In addition to the development of MARC, there were some important changes in attitudes and conditions which made this enlarged activity possible:

- * Greater understanding, both in the Council and among librarians, of the problems involved.
- * Broader experience to draw upon in judging which approaches to solutions appear most promising.

- * The advent of a small but growing body of individuals skilled in both library and systems work.
- * Some efforts among hardware manufacturers to develop equipment suitable for efficient library applications.
- * The emergence of a sufficient body of work in both theory and application on which viable library systems can be built.

Theoretical work on library automation has been conducted all over the country, principally by government-supported projects. The Council, on the other hand, focuses on programs which appear to offer solutions to current library problems, funding those which in its judgment apply the theories and make them work in support of day-to-day operations. This is a much more complicated matter than a layman could believe, as demonstrated by the fact that although the use of electronic computers in library work began about 13 years ago, no major library in this country is yet fully automated. This is the result of some hard facts of life.

- * Very few libraries have computers dedicated to their operations. Those who use computers as a rule share them with other activities of the parent institution and thus are limited by the capacity of the computer and the time available for library use. In addition, difficult and expensive-to-resolve problems can arise when the institution decides to change hardware or software.
- * Very few libraries have budgets large enough to support development in automation. Such development to date has been funded -- often with two or more agencies sharing the cost of one project -- by the Council on Library Resources, the Office of Education, the National Science Foundation, the sponsoring institution, and some others.
- * Until about three years ago, no one knew much about the organization of very large bibliographic files (together with their indexes) in machine-readable form so that there is a proper balance among cost, ease of access at multiple points, acceptable response time, and maintenance of the files. Some of the projects CLR supports (at the

Ohio College Library Center, at Stanford, and the University of Chicago) are sharply focused on exactly these problems, among others, and have developed solutions to some of them -- principally index and file organization and the use of truncated search keys -- to the point that they are being emulated all over the country.

- * Because of the comparatively small market, manufacturers have not produced computer-related equipment and basic software systems designed specifically for library applications. Therefore the library community has been forced to use equipment and systems developed primarily for different kinds of applications.
- * The greatest amount of experience in the use of computers has accrued in the area of data processing (i.e., computation) rather than in the manipulation, storage, and retrieval of strings of alphanumeric characters which represent information. It is of course these latter functions which are pertinent to the needs of libraries. Where other large information files exist, the data records are usually of fixed length and relatively static in nature. Bibliographic records, however, consist mainly of variable-length elements which require frequent update. Most of the recent government-sponsored research and development has focused on the accurate and rapid handling of mathematical calculations, as in space flights; very few such projects have been of assistance to those with large files of information to handle.

Where the computer is used in a library, the approach has usually been to automate one library function at a time. Because of budgetary limitations this is the only approach possible for most libraries now, and librarians are learning automation by doing, which is all to the good. However, it is an approach which incurs large costs without providing correspondingly large benefits, especially at first. For it is an inescapable fact that the maximum benefits a library will ever get from its automation program do not accrue until that program is fully operational. Only then will all the products, by-products, and services (including better services and new ones not economically feasible

in manual systems) become available. To illustrate: A library builds a data base and acquires the necessary computer facilities to produce catalog cards. This is not easy; it is expensive, and takes a long time. The same data base and facilities could support the acquisition, payment, and circulation control functions of the library with relatively minor increases in expenditure. These are the areas in which improvement would have a large (and visible to the user) impact on the library. But they must take a back seat until the initial system is operational. Meanwhile, the librarian spends a great deal of money and has little to show for it. The Council is convinced that, except for a very few of our largest libraries, the only reasonable approach is for libraries to band together in consortia to take advantage of the economies of scale these provide.

The first step in this direction was taken in July 1966. The New England Board of Higher Education had long been interested in developing a computer-based library processing center to serve the state-supported universities of the region. With the advent of MARC and the assurance that cataloging information in machine-readable form would be available in the foreseeable future, it seemed reasonable for the Council to assist in the establishment and implementation of the New England Library Information Network (NELINET). NELINET began with a systems analysis of the involved libraries and went on to a pilot operation in which the libraries received, on an experimental basis, tailored catalog products for titles in the MARC Distribution System. By 1971 NELINET was supplying to over 70 member libraries and affiliated groups custom catalog cards, spine labels, and book labels from MARC tapes.

By the same year the Ohio College Library Center (OCLC), a consortium of academic libraries of that state, had activated the first of its six planned modules for increasing the effectiveness and reducing the cost of basic library

operations through use of a central and shared computer facility. This first operational module is for a computer-based on-line union catalog and shared cataloging system. OCLC's initial developmental aspects had been funded by the Office of Education (OE) and by the consortium membership. During 1972 these costs were shared by OE and the Council. In 1973 new development at OCLC is being funded by the Council alone. Participating Ohio libraries paid for two years for a major portion of the operating costs out of a state subsidy. They now meet all service charges out of their own budgets.

Early in 1971 NELINET and OCLC began to hold discussions to identify the areas within which their separate network programs could be integrated. During the discussions the service and economic objectives of the two groups were reviewed and found to contain a high degree of congruence. Each system was being built to expand the variety of services to users of participating libraries and to lower the rate of rising costs by increasing the productivity of library staff members. Concluding that the similarities between the two systems made it unnecessary for both to invest scarce national and regional resources in redundant research and development activities, the directors of OCLC and NELINET decided to exploit the commonalities of services and economic benefits inherent in both networks by undertaking a feasibility study to determine the transferability of the OCLC system to NELINET and, by extension, to other consortia. The project was funded by the Council in 1972 and successfully demonstrated OCLC's transferability. NELINET is now on-line to the OCLC computer in Columbus and, along with at least eight other regional groups, is looking toward future replication of the OCLC system.

The Ohio College Library Center gives indications of being a most significant library network development, and for this reason has continued to deserve Council support. But there are other reasons:

- * Because OCLC is so potentially significant, and because so many groups are eager to join the undertaking or replicate it, the Council believes it is desirable to be able to influence its development toward the best possible fit in the evolving national system mentioned in the preceding section of this review.
- * The staff at OCLC has demonstrated a strong capability for good library systems work. They have developed and implemented a successful method for the efficient organization of large on-line bibliographic files with on-line update capability, as well as efficient search keys for bibliographic searches.
- * At OCLC the first successful marriage of cathode ray tube terminals suited for library work, telephone lines, and computers took place. A great deal of work, especially theoretical work, along these lines had been done at many other places. At OCLC the published results of these activities were combined with original work, resulting in an efficient system.

To date, OCLC has implemented full cataloging support, based on MARC but also including locally-input cataloging, and flexible bibliographic searches based on author-title, title alone, and LC card number. Serials control, in-process file, and a name-authority index are well along in development. Circulation control and a subject search capability remain in the future.

Although it is a most promising development, OCLC has by no means solved all the problems of library automation and networking. So that other complementary approaches to these problems may be made, the Council at the present time provides support for several additional programs in library automation.

The Ohio College Library Center supports a network of small-to-medium-sized libraries. But the problems of very large libraries are, or at least may be, different and more difficult. For this reason it seemed prudent for the Council to support (with matching funds from the National Endowment for the Humanities) the development of the University of Chicago's Library Data

Management System, whose functions include complex computer file organization, indexing, query and response, and reporting activities -- not initially for a combination of institutions, but for one. Differences in hardware provide another reason for the Council's diversification of support. The dedicated computer at OCLC is a Sigma Five, a member of a fairly obscure family of computers not often found on the campus. The Chicago library, on the other hand, shares with other departments of the university an IBM campus-facility computer. Another difference is in software development. At OCLC the entire software package is tailored for the task; at Chicago the plan is to use the general-purpose operating system already running on the campus computer and to employ a building-block approach for the rest of the software needed.

The overall design for the system is complete. Bibliographic and processing data records are to be created once and then shared in a multiplicity of uses, each record being improved as new increments of data become available during the processes of selection, ordering, receipt, and processing. As the book goes through the various processing steps, an account of its location and status is maintained; this makes it available to the reader even before processing is complete. When processing is complete, data elements no longer needed are stripped off and the permanent records are made available for bibliographic searching and circulation control.

At Chicago the central design factor is the very complex integration of all the files related to the management of books and serials in a library. Discrete data elements are stored once and are brought together in the proper relationship to form a unique record in response to a query for a specific purpose. This requires meticulous planning for the machine links among the various file elements and their indexes. On-line access is planned at several

points in the record: author (to include variant forms of the name), title words, Library of Congress card number, standard book number, etc. Fund accounting and statistics for management are by-products of the processes.

The University of Chicago has accepted a very important concept with regard to library automation: the requirements for computer support to an integrated library system in a large research library are seen to be so comprehensive as to subsume a capability to support many other applications on the campus, especially in administrative data processing. At some other places it was tried the other way around: it was thought that general-purpose software packages acquired to support such things as payroll and student registration would be adequate for library support. But this has proved not to be the case. In library work the sheer size of the files, variability of the records, and complexity of the needed indexes combine to require a system much more powerful and complex than the ordinary business system. At Chicago, therefore, two commercial software packages capable of supporting the library system were acquired. Campus administrative applications are already running under these monitors and the library system is designed to run in harmony with them. Programs for the library applications are being written in-house. The Chicago system is fully compatible with MARC and hence with the other systems the Council supports.

Another major project in library automation currently supported by the Council is BALLOTS (Bibliographic Automation of Large Library Operations using a Time-Sharing System). This too, at present, is a system for a single large library embedded in a campus IBM computer system. Unlike Chicago, where the development is intended to serve only one institution, the BALLOTS designers plan early extension via networking to smaller libraries in the Bay area. Also unlike Chicago, all the BALLOTS software is developed in-house.

Early support for BALLOTS had come from the Office of Education. The Council, in effect, stepped into the breach when, after several years of expensive development, all government support was withdrawn just when the system was ready to begin paying off for the library. NEH agreed to match the Council funds, and the grant was made with the provision that the University commit itself to operating support of the system once this final developmental phase is over.

BALLOTS is being developed and implemented in functional increments. The first three of these -- which, taken together, generate cataloging for the Stanford Libraries from bibliographic records distributed on magnetic tape by the Library of Congress -- became operational in June 1973. They were demonstrated in July to an overflow audience of librarians at a highly successful seminar on BALLOTS. The next module, which will facilitate original cataloging at Stanford, is to be operational in August.

While BALLOTS is considered to be a carefully developed and well designed system, there is some concern among qualified observers that it may be too expensive when fully developed. However, those responsible for the system are convinced that, though costly, it will be less expensive to operate eight or ten years from now than would a manual system.

Smaller projects in automation are also supported by the Council when they show promise and contribute to the overall development of computer application to library use. A recent grant to Bucknell University is an example. Here a low-level effort over several years has produced an excellent circulation control system based on a short bibliographic record. It has also produced a machine-readable record of the complete holdings of the library, and has developed some competent library systems specialists.

These specialists plan to do some experimenting with subject searches with the entire holdings on the line at one time. OCLC, Chicago, and BALLOTS are years away from this point because of their heavy commitment to the development of other parts of their systems. Bucknell also is prepared to let students, the ultimate users, have direct access, through terminals available and familiar to them, to the entire data base. Because of the novelties of these approaches and the Council's interest in developing a capability for subject search, a small grant was made to Bucknell this year, too recently to have produced any report of progress.

In addition to monitoring projects supported by the Council, staff members try to stay abreast of the state of library technology by visiting other libraries where development is taking place. A recent visit to Northwestern University provides a case in point. One of the problems encountered when librarians attempt to run their applications under the general purpose software usually available on campus computers is the fact that the software is so generalized as to require more expensive computer core storage than the library can afford. At Northwestern, genius has been shown in writing library routines so compactly that they fit into the smallest possible compartment in the computer. A comprehensive system for the in-process file, cataloging support, and control of the circulation of the entire book and serials collection operates, on-line, in only 65,000 bytes of core. Northwestern has one of the few operational serials systems which supports all serials processing to include the check-in and control of individual issues. Council staff will describe these techniques in other site visits and will help coordinate the serials activities at Northwestern with the National Serials Data Program.

Project Intrex at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology is the one exception to the Council's general policy of funding only those technology projects which support day-to-day library operations. It was an ambitious

investigation of the bases on which the technical library of the future might be modeled. The Council's first grant, in 1967, was for support of preliminary work on a text-access program.

Primarily, the information contained in libraries is in the form of printed documents or of photographic images of document pages in microform. While future libraries will store some of their information in digitally encoded form, the bulk of their holdings will continue to be in graphic form. An efficient information transfer network should provide access to such data at remote terminals. It should be possible for a user to have material from the central store displayed, either for brief examination or lengthy study, and to obtain a copy to keep. Another requirement is that the text-access system provide rapid service, even if several users simultaneously ask for the same material.

After consultation with an advisory panel established by the Council with the concurrence of M.I.T., the Council made a second grant to include work on the augmented catalog. The purpose of this program, previously supported by the National Science Foundation and others, was to develop and operationally test a remote-access computer-based catalog, differing from a conventional catalog in its breadth of document coverage, depth of information on each entry, and the interactive manner in which users could easily search and retrieve information.

The implementation of these functions led to the utilization of television technology to transmit images from a centrally located automated microform bank to remote user terminals incorporating cathode ray tube displays, mechanisms for rapidly reproducing the microforms, and equipment for converting microforms to full-sized paper copies.

When Council support ended, five years and \$2,246,000 later, the technical feasibility of Project Intrex had been demonstrated and the system was ready, in the Council's judgment and that of the Advisory Committee, for the

move into an operating environment. The project's principals were encouraged to seek other support, either from industry or government, for practical utilization of what had been demonstrated to be an extremely capable, although relatively very expensive, specialized system.

Networks for Interlibrary Cooperation

Cooperation among libraries and groups of libraries takes place, as it has for many years, on a number of levels and in a variety of patterns. When the Council was established the most pressing and immediate problems calling for coordinated action were at the community and state level. To meet the need, CLR in the early 1960s took part in efforts to establish state cooperative library systems which would enable libraries to share in the responsibility for acquiring publications and using them on a state-wide basis. Early studies conducted in Arkansas, Colorado, Arizona, New York, Ohio, and Rhode Island -- with assistance, guidance, and support from the Council -- not only provided solutions for the need of the moment but laid the foundation for the intensive computerized systems now being put into operation.

Special note should be made of the joint support afforded by the Council and the Old Dominion Foundation to assist New York City librarians in developing a major regional plan. The result was the establishment of the New York Metropolitan Reference and Research Agency (METRO), a nonprofit organization to "improve reference and research library services in the New York Metropolitan area by promoting and facilitating utilization of existing resources and developing additional resources." The work of the group has been important to librarians in all regions of the United States.

The most recent Council grant in this activity area was made in 1972 to the Southwestern Library Association (SWLA) for the purpose of encouraging a regional effort by the state librarians and library associations of Texas, Louisiana, Arkansas, Oklahoma, Arizona, and New Mexico. The grant, together with funds and services contributed by SWLA members, made it possible to establish and staff the Southwestern Library Interstate Cooperative Endeavor (SLICE). During its first year SLICE emphasized three program goals:

- * Extending to the six SWLA states the use of MARC-based services developed by the Oklahoma Department of Libraries.
- * Developing a strategy for continuing education for all levels of library staff members in the SLICE area.
- * Initiating and stimulating regional planning and exchange of ideas among the librarians of the six states.

Good progress was made in all areas. The SLICE Office has played an important role in initiating and implementing cooperative programs and in promoting effective communication among the members. This year the Council made a second grant for two-year support of the SLICE Office, the catalytic agent.

One last program will be mentioned here. It provides yet another reason for the lag that exists between the state of the art and its application to libraries.

In late 1969 the Council commissioned a study by the Information Systems Panel of the National Academy of Sciences' (NAS) Computer Science and Engineering Board, in order to determine the current state of computer and system technology as they relate to libraries and information systems. The panel undertook also to identify the roadblocks to more effective and

rapid employment of these technologies for information handling, and to focus national-level attention on appropriate actions to correct identified deficiencies.

The report, Libraries and Information Technology -- a National System Challenge, was published in early 1972. It lists among its conclusions this paragraph:

"The primary bar to development of national computer-based library and information systems is no longer basically a technology-feasibility problem. Rather it is the combination of complex institutional and organizational human-related problems and the inadequate economic/value system associated with these activities. National leadership to solve these problems has not emerged."

As of 1973, it still has not emerged, except in a modest way from the Council.

Modest though it may be, the Council's leadership is strongly felt. Developments are of course influenced by CLR's granting or withholding support. An equally important influence is exerted on a far less formal basis. Since 1968 the Council has added to its staff three very capable systems specialists who keep informed of major projects and developments in library automation. They not only monitor CLR's projects; they also provide the advice, the evaluation, the knowledgeable assistance the Council's constituency has come to expect. In this connection, it seems appropriate to quote from a letter recently received from a well-known former librarian:

"I would like to thank you and your colleagues for the time and assistance which was so willingly given to me and _____ when we visited the Council last week. We obtained more relevant information in an hour from your people than we could get in a day elsewhere."

The kind of assistance referred to here is literally not to be had anyplace else in this country -- unbiased, dispassionate, and completely free of the profit motive. It is currently being provided, by request, to a potential network of important research libraries (Columbia, Harvard, New York Public, and Yale); to groups in Texas, Louisiana, and southeastern United States interested in replicating the OCLC system; to the Washington State Library system; to a Washington, D.C.-based consortium of theological schools.

As has already been stated in this paper, the Council's perception of library development in this country, based on today's reality, is of a loose federation of library cooperatives, each developing on its own schedule, with funds at varying levels from various sources, and with no official guidance on a national basis. As also has been stated, the MARC formats for the transmission of bibliographic information on magnetic tape offer what is practically the only standardizing influence on these disparate developments. The Council sees its role as one of insuring that, as different as these various library developments have to be, they can at least "talk" to each other. It also attempts to prevent wasteful duplication, to promote a rational division of labor, by selecting for support only those projects which seem to lead to the desired goal.

PRESERVATION AND CARE OF THE COLLECTION

The invention of movable type was not, as is commonly believed, an entirely beneficent factor in the history of the book, for the fact that books could be produced more and more rapidly meant that more and more paper was needed. This ever-accelerating rate of use brought about changes in the way paper was produced and in the materials from which it was made. The result was a continuing decline in quality to the point where book papers produced hundreds of years ago are in many instances in excellent condition today, while those manufactured fifty years ago are all too often literally falling apart, and those only a few years old are in large percentage already badly weakened.

Much effort by highly reputed investigators went into trying to determine the cause and cure for deteriorating paper. But it was the painstaking work of William J. Barrow, a document restorer of Richmond, Virginia, that did most to establish with certainty the central role of acidity in the deterioration process. Barrow, working alone, also determined that treating paper with calcium hydroxide and calcium bicarbonate would neutralize its acid nature and build in an alkaline reserve, thus halting deterioration.

In 1957 CLR, acting through the Virginia State Library, began to support Barrow's work. As a first step in his Council-sponsored research, he made a careful evaluation of book papers produced in the first half of the twentieth century. Working with the counsel of a committee of scientists and library administrators, Barrow revealed the serious loss of strength that infected modern papers: papers used in the test group of books from the first decade of the 1900s had lost 96 percent of their strength by 1957, and papers produced in 1940-49 had lost 64 percent of their strength.

The Council continued to support William Barrow's work and was rewarded by the development of specifications for manufacture of "permanent and durable" paper, with an expected useful life of 300 years. In May 1959 the experimental paper mill of the Herty Foundation in Savannah, Georgia, made a first trial run of paper meeting those specifications. Today there are a number of commercially produced permanent and durable papers.

After Barrow's death in 1967 the Council continued to fund the work of the laboratory bearing his name. It appears that the laboratory is now (June 1973) close to perfecting a vapor process for deacidifying whole books in quantity at low cost without deleterious side effects.

The laboratory's work has not been restricted to programs related to acid in paper. Researchers there have also investigated other preservation matters of interest to libraries, including aging of adhesives used in binding and the development of performance standards for bindings.

Nor have the Council's activities in the realm of preservation and conservation been centered solely on the Barrow Laboratory. To the contrary, CLR has supported a host of programs covering the full range of conservation interests. Here is a selection of some of the most significant:

- * An investigation of European library binding practices.
- * Preparation and publication of two books on the care and repair of library materials (through the Library Technology Program).
- * Investigation of the problems of research library catalog renovation, preservation, and maintenance.
- * Study of early limp vellum binding practices for the purposes of conservation, with possible implications for modern binding techniques (in progress).

- * Preparation of a complete workshop manual describing all aspects of the restoration of printed books and parchment manuscripts (in progress).
- * Equipment for the Preservation Research Office at the Library of Congress (in progress).

The most recent grant for conservation and restoration was made to a library consortium of the New England States for 50 percent of the initial funding of a Document Restoration Center which would perform preservation and repair processes on documents submitted by member institutions. (The Consortium itself will supply the remaining half of the funds.) The Center is an opportunity to apply in a very practical way the techniques developed by earlier Council grants to other organizations. It is hoped that it will serve also as a model institution of its type and thereby provide guidance to other regional consortia concerned with preservation.

It should be noted here that microforms are also an important part of the answer to the problem of deteriorating materials. Besides being the most practical means of conserving newspapers, microfilm is the only feasible way to date of dealing with very badly deteriorated books which, while intellectually important, do not warrant or permit the kind of costly restoration procedures used for truly rare volumes. Although it is generally conceded that microforms cannot always be substituted for paper copies, it is possible to make adequate paper facsimiles of most documents by means of automatic or page-at-a-time microform-to-hard copy-printers. Microforms are especially flexible media; the same film which serves as a master preservation copy can also be easily copied to produce a printing master from which any number of dissemination copies can be economically printed at any time. But microforms too are subject to deterioration and programs are needed that will deal with the preservation of film materials.

The quantities of publications that will eventually require preservation of one type or another are so vast as to defy attempts to save them all. Undoubtedly hard decisions on priorities will be demanded at times when needs are great and resources for meeting them are limited. Work in this important area should be continued in such a way as to provide all concerned with the problem the information that will make possible informed decisions.

ADMINISTRATION AND MANAGEMENT

The responsibilities involved in running a library are no less complex than those of running a business or industrial enterprise of similar size. Unique to the library are the intellectually challenging fields of bibliography, the classification of knowledge, its storage, and provision for its use. Added to these are the general administrative problems which must be dealt with in any viable operation.

Most academic and public librarians are book- or information-oriented; their background generally is in the academic disciplines and they have had little or no special training for management.* As long as libraries were small and simply organized, management problems were of relatively minor significance and could be handled satisfactorily on an ad hoc basis. But expanding programs, new users with new needs, and the multiplication in the size and roles of libraries during the past quarter century have contributed to a real management crisis.

The Council has always been alert to the need for support of administrative development in libraries, and until 1968 directed its grants to meet the requirements of specific aspects of library administration: planning for buildings and for space utilization, budgeting, projecting for future needs, developing personnel practices and policies, simplifying work methods, mapping storage procedures, dealing with insurance and legal requirements. For example:

- * An early grant was for a study of book charging and circulation systems. The ensuing report provided guidance in the elimination of inefficiencies which consume excessive amounts of time, thus freeing staff for more and better service to the public.

*Special libraries and librarians, with the exception of the national libraries, have not been given significant attention by the Council and are thus at present not given an important role in our review.

- * Buildings and space constitute costly initial investment and continuing operating expenses. The Council has stimulated and supported basic publications on academic library buildings. Its grants have also enabled libraries to develop systems for better use of space, for investigations of cooperative storage of seldom used materials, and for systematic retirement of older ones.
- * Savings for nearly all libraries have resulted from Council-supported studies on damage to publications through fire and other means.
- * Unified statistical compilation and standards for library service are essential if libraries are to evaluate their services and prepare well justified budgets. When the Council supported its first study of library statistics, there were more than 140 organizations compiling and issuing unrelated library data. In part as a result of CLR projects, these have since been reduced to a few major services. Its support has been instrumental as well in the development of a variety of library standards, including those for library bindings, cataloging rules, school libraries, and those promulgated by Committee Z39 of the American National Standards Institute.
- * Small public libraries serving villages and towns constitute the largest class of libraries in the country. Their directors as well as local officials have been eager to utilize the newest and best in library practices but these, as they have developed, have not been tailored to their special needs. In cooperation with the American Library Association, the Council supported a Small Libraries Project to provide aid and guidance to this group of institutions. A series of manuals was issued which has been used in most of the small libraries of the United States and Canada for improvement of their management practices.
- * In some areas -- library laws, insurance, book storage -- Council grants have supported the basic research and the compilation of information for developments important to virtually all libraries.

Thus, although the Council gives priority attention to the problems of academic and research libraries, almost every kind of library has partici-

pated in one or another of the CLR-supported management projects. Public, school, children's, special, law, medical -- all have benefited from the Council's activities.

Academic Libraries

In 1968 the Council embarked on discussions leading to a series of related projects which constitute a major effort to help academic libraries restudy, reorganize, and redirect their management efforts into proven efficient methods. In doing so the Council has recognized that librarianship is a service-oriented profession, with an in-built sensitivity and even resistance to a wholesale approach to management improvement. There is, quite properly, the concern that the essential service element may be sacrificed to efficiency. The Council has therefore attempted to serve as a guide to and supporter of librarians in the effort to change library attitudes toward management practices. It also recognizes that the techniques of good administration cannot be lifted bodily from business or government and applied to libraries without important alterations. Thus an early phase of the attack on the problem centered on work with top-flight management specialists to help them gain understanding of the nature of libraries and their needs.

But academic libraries do not operate in a vacuum; they are parts of much larger institutions from which they derive their funds and to which they are responsible. It appeared essential, then, to involve college and university administration intimately in the overall program from its beginning. The first grant in this major effort was to the Association of Research Libraries (ARL), whose membership then consisted of the 85 most important academic and research libraries in this country and Canada. With the funds ARL engaged the services of Booz, Allen & Hamilton, a leading

management consultant firm, for a preliminary study of management practices in large university libraries. One of the conditions imposed by the Council was that there be immediately established an advisory committee composed of leading academic librarians, selected by ARL, and university presidents, selected by the American Council on Education (ACE), which cosponsored the study. Those designated to serve were, for the librarians, Warren J. Haas of Columbia, Douglas Bryant of Harvard, Herman Fussler of the University of Chicago, John McDonald of the University of Connecticut, and Robert Vosper of the University of California at Los Angeles. The ACE group consisted of Willard J. Boyd of the University of Iowa, Howard W. Johnson of the Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Richard W. Lyman of Stanford, and Allen M. Cartter of New York University.

The committee worked with the Booz, Allen team every step of the way, supplying the insights, guidance and specialized knowledge that were needed as the investigators moved into what was, for them, largely unexplored territory. It proved to be a remarkably effective partnership, and the resultant report provided a useful foundation for further efforts to improve management practices, to the ultimate benefit of those who use and those who operate research libraries.

The study led to the establishment within ARL of the Office of University Library Management Studies (OMS), now in its third year and supported by Council funds. The current grant to ARL for the Office stipulates that the Association itself begin to take some responsibility for financing, with the hope that in the not too distant future OMS will no longer be dependent on Council aid. It is useful to note here that many of the activities carried forward by the Office are ones which CLR would otherwise be called upon for funding. It has seemed to us, however, that such programs

are far more effective if they emanate from an organization like ARL, composed of the libraries that will profit from them.

A request from Columbia University and ARL provided the opportunity for taking the next step in the logical development of the program: a case study of some management aspects of one large university library. The Council contracted with Booz, Allen & Hamilton, which by now had a fair amount of useful experience in the area, to conduct a study of the organization and staffing of the Columbia University Libraries. In addition to its value to Columbia, the study provided important on-the-job training to the then newly appointed director of OMS and served as well as a pilot which other large university libraries may follow at considerably less expense. To expedite this, and out of the experience, the OMS has developed a management review and analysis program and manual by means of which academic libraries may perform, with the assistance and guidance of OMS personnel, self-administered studies of their operations as they work toward better management practices.

Another outgrowth of the Columbia study was the establishment at that university of a Libraries Planning Office, to be funded initially by a three-year grant from the Council. The need for such an office had been demonstrated in the study, and was further reinforced by the University's decision to bring together all the components concerned with information resources and the information handling capabilities that are required to support Columbia's educational program. The University Librarian was designated Vice President for Information Services and given responsibility for library service, computer service, technical aids to instruction, and other specialized teaching and learning resources. The Planning Office will, it is hoped, provide a continuing and sophisticated effort to anticipate the full range of library and information resources available and of

potential use, and to plan for their effective utilization in the context of University needs and financial constraints. The University has committed itself to provide for the continuing operation of the Office at the conclusion of the grant period.

Because the academic library holds a unique position in its parent institution as far as its functions, facilities, and purpose are concerned, the Council decided that there is much to be gained by establishing within an academic library a model research and development unit, where library problems and plans may be dealt with in the library framework by a library-oriented staff. It was for this reason that the Council in 1969 and again in 1971 provided funds to establish and operate a research and development unit in the Joint University Libraries (JUL), serving Vanderbilt University and Scarritt and George Peabody Colleges, in Nashville, Tennessee.

The unit has performed important work in such areas as personnel policies, administrative procedures, acquisitions statistics gathering, modification of the JUL accounting and management information systems, and program budgeting concepts. During the past year a systems specialist was added to the staff, thus furnishing another dimension to the activities. Because of its effectiveness, the Vanderbilt University Chancellor recently turned over to JUL a large grant the university had received for allocation to the department or activity which, in the judgment of the Chancellor and his advisors, would use it most profitably in helping the university achieve general academic excellence.

Another kind of approach to effective management was made in a grant for a training program just completed at the Cornell University Libraries. Guided by the Center for Planning and Development of the American Manage-

ment Association, the twelve-month program of staff development included five-day retreats and seminars, library visits by consultants, planning sessions, and the like. Its purpose was not only to give the Cornell University Libraries staff a clearer idea of both short- and long-term objectives and strategies, but to help them acquire the necessary skills for continued effective planning. It is of course too early to evaluate long-term effects. But the University Librarian, in his final report to the Council, says: "The results were invaluable to Cornell and went far to strengthen its management program ... The benefits ... have already spread far beyond Cornell itself ..." through replication by other libraries, published articles, speeches, seminars, and wide distribution of the report.

The Council has also utilized the services of existing centers in attempting to find solutions to management problems. A grant to the Library Research Unit at the University of Lancaster in England was made in late 1970 for a research project focusing on the factors that tend to encourage or discourage use of available services, the factors that are within the power of libraries to influence, and on how the impact of proposed changes in library and information services can be predicted. These are complex problems which have not thus far been solved by either subjective or empirical methods. Lancaster's approach is one which may provide libraries with highly significant and useful information.

Earlier in this section reference was made to the importance of statistics to libraries as they engage in the budget-making process. Equally important is the ability to use current data in order to project for future needs. This requirement is as important for academic libraries as for any others, and thus the Council contracted with Mathematica, Inc., for a study of the economics of library operations. The report will be published in

Fall 1973 by the American Council on Education, and its Introduction states in part:

"This volume represents what we believe to be as complete and thorough an analysis as possible of the available economic data on college and university libraries. In the course of our study, we have examined the data for comprehensiveness and consistency, we have investigated their intertemporal behavior, both as a basis for projection and as an instrument for long-range planning, and we have constructed a set of analytic interrelationships which permitted us to derive statistical estimates of the interrelations of some of the most critical economic variables relating to library operations. In particular, in the course of this last step, we have provided relationships explaining statistically the determination of such variables as the size of library budgets and the magnitude of their professional staff.

"It is hoped that the results of our analysis can be helpful at a number of levels. They can be used by individual librarians in making their plans for their own institutions, by college and university administrations in anticipating the future fiscal needs of their libraries or in evaluating the financial consequences of decisions on overall institutional policy, and they can assist in the work of organizations representing the librarians, helping them to make their case for the resources they need, and helping them to determine lines of research that will be useful in planning for the future."

Each of the programs discussed above has had impact well beyond the site institution. There has been a remarkable exchange of information and cross-pollination among them, further augmenting the effectiveness of the overall plan. It is our hope that, as the opportunity arises, a program similar in purpose but probably different in design, may be developed for non-ARL university libraries and for four-year colleges.

THE INTERFACE: LIBRARIES AND THEIR USERS

The last two decades have been a time of enormous pressure on libraries, pressure resulting from rapidly changing patterns of use and the exponential increase in published materials in the face of serious fiscal restrictions. Because of this, much emphasis in recent years has been on management, computerization, networks, technology -- in general, efficiency of operation. The Council is concerned that these elements in the library structure be recognized for what they in fact are -- the mechanisms which make it possible for the library to help users meet their educational, cultural, professional, or personal requirements for information and knowledge. For libraries exist to serve people.

The Introduction to the Council's 16th Annual Report puts it this way:

"Efficiency and economical operations are only the means to an end, to our hoped-for goal of helping libraries in this country and elsewhere shift more effectively from a pressing concentration upon their own internal problems to their proper purpose of promoting scholarship and inculcating learning. For if humanists and scientists of all disciplines are to make important and needed contributions to society, they must continue to have adequate access to the world's literature and knowledge, and in this libraries must play the key role."

Through June 1972 the Council expended nearly \$3,000,000 -- just under 20 percent of its available program funds -- on projects which attempt to respond to the fact that each type of library and each library in a type has a special clientele whose requirements must be identified and met. Some of these are described on the pages that follow.

The College Library

"The library should be the keystone in the process of liberal education. It not only supports the programs in all the academic departments but is the principal means by which their teaching can be extended in depth or breadth. The instruction that can be given in the classroom is necessarily bounded by arbitrary time factors; there are theoretically no limits to the learning that can be obtained through a library.

"What is more important, the library can open the way for continuity between a student's college experience and his intellectual growth throughout his life. Continuing self-instruction is essential for successful living in an age of challenge to all concepts, and an individual who can use a library stands the best chance of meeting that challenge, in the face of ephemeral facts and instant ideologies.

"But the library cannot be merely a passive partner in the educational process. It must have its own positive program; it must have dynamic and imaginative leadership. However, optimum effectiveness can be obtained only by coordinated endeavor on the part of administration, faculty, and library staff, based upon clearly defined institutional policies."

When these paragraphs, part of an internal paper, were written late in 1968, little was being done on a wide basis, either by or for the profession, to help libraries achieve a more focal point in education. There was -- and is -- a group that has promoted the proposition that the library is the college. The Council prefers to believe that the library is a major part of the college. To help it become the important part it should be, the Council in 1969 initiated the College Library Program (CLP) and with the National Endowment for the Humanities established a joint \$1,400,000 fund from which matching grants could be made to individual colleges and universities whose proposed programs showed promise of achieving CLP's goal and meeting its standards.

By spring of 1973 thirteen colleges and universities were working on projects developed through the cooperative efforts of their librarians, faculty members, and administrations. As the program requires, all have matched the five-year CLR-NEH grants with equal amounts, over and above the regular library appropriation. And all are directed toward building on present library resources to achieve a more productive and relevant-to-learning place for the library in the academic life of the institutions. The funds may not be used for adding to collections or for programs which do not relate to the humanities.*

The institutions receiving grants thus far range from a new experimental college -- Hampshire, in Amherst, Massachusetts -- to older schools like Brown University; from Davidson College in the east to Jamestown College in the west; and from a rapidly developing state university -- Eastern Michigan -- to the well-established University of Colorado. Four predominantly black schools are among the thirteen using this support to improve the level of their educational work. Wabash College is also participating in the program, but not through the joint grant. The college has a policy against accepting federal funds, and the Council alone provides the support, which Wabash matches.

It is already apparent that the program is helping libraries play an increasingly important part in the education of undergraduates. It has served also to make faculty members and administrators more aware of the library's proper place in the academic constellation, and this not only because of

*NEH defines "humanities" to include, but not limited to, the study of the following: language, both modern and classical; linguistics; literature, history; jurisprudence; philosophy, archeology; comparative religion; ethics; the history, criticism, theory, and practice of the arts; those aspects of the social sciences which have humanistic content and employ humanistic methods; and the study and application of the humanities to the human environment with particular attention to the relevance of the humanities to the current conditions of national life.

the effectiveness of the projects. The fact of the award itself, coming as it does from two prestigious organizations, has added in some eyes to the stature of the library, and the amount of interest engendered by the projects has opened other eyes to its value. All of the institutions thus far participating report numerous requests for information as well as visits from librarians who want to learn more about what is going on. The director of the program at Eastern Michigan University, who has taken leadership in organizing yearly workshops on the subject, estimates that there are at least 140 colleges and universities at present developing the kinds of projects initiated by the Council in the College Library Program. But most important of all is the gratifying student response to the greater degree of participation and higher visibility of the library in the learning experience. It is a response that leads one to believe that the program has met a previously unexpressed need. And that, after all, is the point.

M.I.T. Model Engineering Library Project Intrex, which is discussed in the section on Automation and Networks, experimented with the development of new technology and equipment for the storage and retrieval of documents and information. At the Council's insistence, M.I.T. provided for use of this technology and equipment in a working library through the establishment of a model library within its new Barker Engineering Library. The model library experiment is significant for two reasons:

- * It is taking advanced techniques and methods out of the laboratory and into the library, where they are available for everyday use.
- * Its experience provides other libraries with information about the problems involved in shifting from a conventional library program to one which utilizes modern technology, including computers.

An interesting by-product of the program has been the development of specialized bibliographic guides which not only serve to introduce a user to the literature of specific fields, but also to acquaint him more or less painlessly with the library and its effective use. Library Pathfinders have been used successfully by libraries throughout the country. They are now being distributed by a commercial publisher, with royalties earmarked for the future operations of the Model Engineering Library.

The Public Library

In the past two decades public librarians have been faced with serious challenges and problems at every level of their work. In addition to the physical and fiscal problems posed by the unprecedented increase in the quantity of publications, they have had to deal with the social, educational, and political questions that must be answered if they are to serve a changing clientele with different and expanding needs.

In 1971 the Council and the National Endowment for the Humanities provided funds for a critical study by the Public Library Association of the goals of public library service. The resulting report, published in 1972, is both a challenge and a preliminary guide to public librarians. Analytical and critical, it suggests the steps that must be taken to return public libraries to their essential community role. Public librarians have formed action groups to expand and carry out the recommendations for changes in public library responsibilities, services, and organization.

The University Around the Corner Increased attention here and in England to the development of nontraditional study at the college level provides an opportunity for public libraries to intensify, expand, and develop

services in adult education. Public libraries, although they have long considered themselves "the people's universities," have not often given sufficient attention to this facet of program.

The Council was instrumental in stimulating the involvement of libraries in the early planning stages of nontraditional educational activity. Several years ago, when widespread U.S. interest in the subject surfaced and began to develop, CLR acted to bring together the nontraditional planners and the public library leaders. Then, with the College Entrance Examination Board (CEEB) and NEH, the Council supported an experimental program at the Dallas Public Library to determine the role the American public library might play in external degree work. The Library has worked with educational institutions in the Dallas area to develop its own in-house programs and services which directly assist those wishing to study for credit outside the normal framework. Public library participation in adult education has generally centered on providing bibliographic services and reading materials, not on direction and guidance of the individual. The Dallas program broke new ground with its offering of tutorial and workshop services.

The two-year project now near completion has pointed up the necessity for libraries and educational institutions to work out new methods for cooperating with each other and with adults interested in working independently for credit. It is also clear that if libraries are adequately to serve this emerging educational need, steps must be taken to provide staff with training in academic counseling and guidance, to develop specialized materials, and to establish a central coordinating body to serve as a central source of communication and information.

Thus the Council joined with the College Entrance Examination Board to plan and establish in 1972 the Office of Library Independent Study and

Guidance Projects whose purpose is to provide the materials, training, and other planning resources public libraries need to become effective community learning centers. The Office is supported through joint funding by CLR, NEH, CEEB, and the Bureau of Libraries and Learning Resources of the Office of Education.

In this, its first year, the Office plans to develop models of service and to inventory the library resources now available for aiding those who wish to carry out independent study. In its second and third years it will stimulate training, demonstration, and the setting up of an independent study system in public libraries throughout the country. It is expected that the work of the Office will make it possible for libraries to be full partners with education in developing nontraditional study programs.

New York City Information Centers Drastic alterations in inner city life, the expansion of suburbia, and social, political, and educational developments in metropolitan areas are directly challenging the established role of the public library.

In their efforts to adjust themselves to the changing public needs for information, libraries have been experimenting with new types of information service centers. Most ambitious of these programs is the New York Citizens' Information Centers, developed jointly by representatives of the mayor's office, educators, and librarians. The original plan was for a \$10,000,000 project, supported by \$7,500,000 of federal funds to be matched with \$2,500,000 from other sources. The program would enable public libraries of three New York City boroughs, with the help of a sophisticated computerized data bank, to provide through the library branches requested information on a wide variety of services heretofore unavailable centrally. For example, a

citizen could obtain directly from the branch library immediate response to questions he might have concerning his veterans' benefits; it would not be necessary for him to go through the often complicated, time-consuming, and frustrating process involved in attempting to communicate personally with government. Planners requested and received a grant of \$300,000 from the Council on Library Resources to assist in launching the project.

The advent of revenue sharing meant that the promised federal contribution was no longer available for the purpose, but the city decided to go ahead nonetheless, using its own funds (on a smaller scale) and limiting the project to one borough -- Brooklyn. The mayor of New York and his staff officially inaugurated the program in April 1973 in a ceremony at the Brooklyn Public Library.

The Council has made this somewhat unusual grant in the belief that traditional uses of the library will not be adversely affected by the enlargement of its service through the information centers. Rather it is hoped that the person who comes to the library initially to seek information about personal or local problems will soon come to see and make use of the library in its more customary role.

Books by Mail This general thrust to bring the library's information directly to the public -- to reach beyond library walls -- is shown also in the rapidly developing system of providing books by mail.

Although public library branches have brought services closer to all members of the public, many citizens in any city are not library users. To make access easy for all citizens, the San Antonio Public Library developed a Books-by-Mail program. The Council supported the project as a pilot effort to determine if nonusers could be reached through book circulation via the

postal system. Any resident of the county, card carrier or not, could mail or telephone to the library requests which would be filled by mail.

The experiment was highly successful. Service was fast, books were returned more promptly than those circulated in the customary manner, cost was moderate, and numerous new users were introduced to the library. The San Antonio Public has continued the program as part of its regular service.

An important result of the experiment has been the initiation of numerous mail delivery systems by local, county, state, and regional libraries. Interest in this kind of service is so high that an informal organization of books-by-mail libraries has been established, reporting regularly on various types of mail service. A small grant from the Council is making it possible for the group to meet just prior to the 1973 ALA meeting to discuss ongoing programs, evaluate activities, and provide nationwide information concerning books-by-mail. As of May 25, 1973, 116 individuals representing 113 libraries in 39 states and Canada had registered for the conference.

Los Angeles Public Library Community Study If there is a common thread running through this discussion of public libraries, it is surely the changing demands of users. It seems reasonable then, in developing new branch libraries, to plan from the earliest stages for them to meet community needs. This will be done in a project soon to begin at the Los Angeles Public Library. The Council and the Educational Facilities Laboratories are funding a new analytic approach which utilizes established sociological tools to study the needs, goals, motivations, and concerns of the people living in three neighborhoods where the Library has scheduled new branches. It is hoped that this will result in programs and buildings which will make the libraries a vital part of community life.

Library Tools

Thus far the discussion in this section has centered on activities undertaken by libraries to help them meet new needs. Now it turns to projects designed to assist libraries and users to make fuller use of materials already at hand or to make more efficient the usual rules and procedures of librarians.

Union Lists: It is neither possible nor particularly useful for every library to own every book or periodical, but it is possible for libraries to share their resources. So that users may discover which libraries hold wanted materials, union lists have been developed -- bibliographies which contain a record of the combined holdings of libraries in various fields of knowledge. One of the most important of these is the Union List of Serials in Libraries in the United States and Canada, which supplies libraries and scholars with information about and access to the files of 156,000 different periodicals and journals in almost a thousand libraries. Beginning with a first grant in 1958, the Council provided expert guidance and support at every stage of development, investing nearly \$300,000 in the work over an eight-year period.

Other CLR grants have made it possible for librarians and scholars to prepare additional union lists (e.g., National Union List of Manuscript Collections) as well as bibliographies of music resources, art materials, and similar specialized resources.

Selection Aids for College Libraries: College libraries must have available for use materials required by the curriculum; they must also anticipate needs so that necessary publications may be on the shelves when needed. The problems involved in selecting the right books are further compounded by the limited funds the libraries have for acquisitions, for mistakes are

costly. In the late 1950s when the Council was established, academic libraries had an urgent need for a new basic book list and for a periodical which would provide them with selection aids and reviews of currently published materials. Both of these needs were met through projects supported by the Council in cooperation with the American Library Association and academic specialists. Books for College Libraries, listing more than 53,000 titles, was published in 1967 and continues to be an important selection tool.

Basic lists like Books for College Libraries furnish librarians with guides for developing well-rounded collections in all fields and in purchasing those books which are regarded as most useful and fundamental. Beyond this, however, is the need for timely authoritative evaluations of current publications in every subject field. The costs of establishing such a service were too high to be underwritten by libraries, and commercial publishers expressed vast disinterest. Hence the Council provided the guidance and the funding which led to the establishment in 1964 of CHOICE, a monthly book selection journal published by the Association of College and Research Libraries, a division of the American Library Association.

According to its title page, "The journal seeks to provide a reference and advisory guide ... of significant current publications in terms of the relative place of a book in the context of both the literature of the field and the undergraduate library collection. One of CHOICE's greatest services lies in briefly comparing a new title to earlier titles in the field ... These books are evaluated by college faculty members currently or formerly engaged in undergraduate teaching at academic institutions throughout the United States and Canada." By 1969 the publication was self-supporting. And by March 1973, the completion of its ninth year of publication, it had reviewed slightly over 50,000 books.

While Books for College Libraries and CHOICE provide academic librarians with extremely useful tools for book selection, both demand that the using libraries develop their own selection procedures to determine which of the listed books will be acquired. Unfortunately, many of the country's most understocked college libraries are also understaffed, and often both the time and the expertise to make the required decisions are lacking. It was to meet this special need that the Council developed a plan for the Core Collection -- the 40,000 basic titles any four-year liberal arts college must have in its library if it intends to provide students with an adequate education. This, of course, is not meant to include all the books a library should have; only those it must have. A 1969 grant to the American Library Association covers development of the list and its preparation for publication. The information is being recorded on computer tape, and a book catalog will be produced from machine-readable records. Final editing is now being completed, and publication of "A Core Collection" by ALA is expected in the spring of 1974. It is believed that the machine-readable format will be useful for many purposes other than the original publication for which the grant was made.

So that the Collection may remain current, ALA has arranged for the CHOICE staff to produce supplements to the Core Collection at regular intervals, thus assuring its continuing timeliness.

Building Collections

One of the earliest determinations the Council had to make was that it could not address itself to the local requirements of individual libraries by providing funds for "normal" purposes -- the construction of buildings, procurement of collections, or strengthening of staffs. The needs of all libraries for better buildings, more books, more staff are so overwhelming that no private organization, certainly not the Council, can begin to meet them.

However, it is sometimes possible to initiate or support programs which will assist the libraries themselves to find ways of satisfying these needs. It might be through the publication of a book devoted to library buildings, like the recently issued Academic Library Buildings: A Guide to Architectural Issues and Solutions. Or it might be through support of some of the collection-building programs described below. For libraries can be effective -- in any environment -- only when they have available an adequate supply of appropriate books and other materials.

The United States Book Exchange, Inc., (USBE) was set up in 1948 to serve as a center for the exchange among libraries of duplicates of books and periodicals having potential value for research but with insufficient market value to make them attractive to the antiquarian book trade. Its stock includes millions of items and it serves over 1,000 institutions, American and foreign. The economics of the operation were from the beginning a source of concern. With the help of two Council grants, in 1957 and again in 1971, USBE was able to study its operations and procedures, to re-define its activities, and to explore possibilities and bases for future expansion and financing. As of 1973, USBE reports that this help from the Council has made it possible to maintain services on a self-supporting basis.

With increasing general interest in world affairs, the development of area study programs, and the expansion of the publishing industry's output in every part of the world, academic libraries had to find new ways of acquiring foreign publications. It was decided that large-scale cooperative efforts were needed to locate, purchase, and share publications.

The Farmington Plan was such an effort on the part of sixty American libraries. When it began in 1947 the Plan was the only major project of the kind. By 1959 the participants were acutely aware of deficiencies in it and the need for major changes. It was time to ascertain whether the Plan had

in fact brought to this country the publications it was intended it should bring, whether those publications were generally accessible to researchers, whether the mechanisms of the operation needed revision, and whether its scope should be reduced or broadened. The Council supported a survey and evaluation which resulted in a changed and improved activity.

In 1958 Congress authorized, as part of Public Law 480, an unprecedented program to use U.S.-owned foreign currencies for the purchase, servicing, and distribution of books, periodicals, and related materials to American university and research libraries. Authorization was only the first phase. Next was the appropriation to carry out the work -- and Congress failed to act. Concerned by the delay, research libraries and the American Council of Learned Societies obtained a small grant from the Council to allow Dr. Mortimer Graves to study the law and assist learned societies and libraries in their planning with respect to the activities it covered. In effect, his study and report stimulated the Congress to appropriate the needed funds in 1961. The Council continued its interest in the ways libraries could best exploit this valuable resource and supported a second study by Dr. Graves in 1967. The report was published in 1969; its summary has special significance in 1973:

"Our effort must now be to create a new kind of cooperation between these disciplinary and areal concerns. Moreover, in the case of operations of this character, supported by public funds, we must always assume a responsibility to assure that they do not become the plaything of too limited interests. The concerns of librarians, scholars, and scientists are an important though not a sufficient consideration.

"It is not overly extravagant to suggest that the American Library Establishment may well turn out to be our first line of defense. The richest and most powerful society in history, called to responsibility, if not leadership, in the spherical, scientific, social, secular, dynamic,

crowded, and contentious world promised us by the twenty-first century, must develop the facilities for knowing that world as completely as possible. Of these our libraries form not the least important element. Only with understanding can we escape disaster; without it fifty more Koreas and Vietnams lie just around the corner."

INTERNATIONAL ACTIVITIES

Library activities are fundamentally the same the world over. Librarians -- no matter where they are or what language they speak -- are agreed about their functions, use more or less the same procedures in carrying them out and the same terms to describe them. There are indeed large differences, from country to country, in levels of requirements and the methods employed to meet them. But the degree of community of interest far exceeds any differences, and the techniques and procedures developed in one area of the world are to a significant extent transferable. Thus cooperation on an international level is vital -- as much for the most sophisticated systems as for those in earlier stages of development.

It is not due to chance that the recent enormous progress in solving many long-standing problems which have plagued thoughtful librarians in most countries for years has coincided with the Council's existence. For the Council's interest and financial help, judiciously applied, have succeeded in breaking many logjams and clearing the way ahead for many promising developments.

It is somewhat misleading to try to distinguish "international activities" as a separate phase of the Council's work. Most of CLR's activities in encouraging new initiatives have international implications and great international importance. All librarians, elsewhere as here, are vitally interested in, for example, the MARC and RECON projects at the Library of Congress, Cataloging in Publication, the application of computers and other advanced technology to library work, the concept of consortia to make the most efficient use of scarce manpower and funds, the adaptation of management techniques for use in libraries, and other areas in which the Council has been giving its

help and encouragement. In this section, however, the discussion will be limited to the significant grants made by the Council over the years specifically intended to promote international cooperation.

CLR's first important venture in international action had to do with cataloging, the process which arranges the information in a library so that it may be readily found by or for the user. In this as in all the processes employed by libraries to serve their users, uniformity of practice is not only desirable but essential. For now more than ever scholarship recognizes no geographic boundaries, and its requirements are truly international in scope.

The International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA) had for several years been working on the coordination of cataloging practices when the Council in 1958 provided that organization with funds for a preliminary meeting to make careful plans for the 1961 International Conference on Cataloguing Principles in Paris, which was also supported by the Council. The Paris Conference was attended by more than 100 participants from 53 countries (with over 100 observers from 20 countries), and resulted in a substantial measure of agreement in an area where agreement had previously seemed almost impossible. The Conference report was widely circulated and contributed greatly to the present successful progress toward coordination of cataloging practices in many parts of the world. A further grant in 1969 enabled the IFLA Committee on Uniform Cataloguing Rules to organize a meeting of specialists in Copenhagen to review developments since the 1961 Conference and to examine the prospects for further advances through standardization and mechanization. Significant progress was made at this meeting toward agreement on standards of bibliographical description for catalog entries. An additional result was

development of a proposal for the establishment of a permanent secretariat for the IFLA Committee on Cataloguing to furnish needed continuity and coordination of its important work. A Council grant made the secretariat possible. International Cataloguing, published quarterly by the secretariat at a modest subscription rate, provides a forum for feedback and discussion as well as dissemination of information about worldwide planning for and development of cataloging standards. The sharing of cataloging between countries and institutions, now rendered more feasible and in some ways more complex by the adoption of computerized procedures, has been materially advanced by these developments.

The Council has assisted with additional important work in the establishment of other international standards for libraries and documentation centers. These developments are discussed in the section of this report which deals with National Library Services.

There are other international organizations in the field of books and documentation which the Council has supported with important results. One of these is RISM (Repertoire International des Sources Musicales), a joint venture of the International Association of Music Libraries and the International Musicological Society. The 30 volumes of this publication will survey the sources for the history of music up to 1800. Another is the International Council on Archives, whose 1966 Extraordinary Congress and two resultant committees (to facilitate scholarly access to archives, and to study methods for the publication of archival sources) received financial assistance from the Council. The Pan American Union has also been the recipient of Council grants made for the purpose of improving the capabilities of Latin American libraries.

Because of the implications for libraries the Council has followed with interest the work of the Federation Internationale de Documentation (FID), to whose thirty-first conference, held in Washington in 1965, the Council made a financial contribution; and the development of a plan put forward by the International Council of Scientific Unions (ICSU) and Unesco to create a worldwide science information system, covering primarily natural and technical sciences. Members of the Council's staff have attended meetings at Unesco on this latter development, as well as other international conferences dealing with various aspects of library work. On two occasions the Council has provided support for attendance at the International Congress of Orientalists. The XXVII Congress, held at the University of Michigan in 1967, attracted nearly 2500 specialists. From the Council's point of view an important feature was the inclusion of a panel of librarians which gained the favorable attention of many of the scholars present and led to the formation of the International Association of Orientalist Librarians. The following Congress was held at Canberra in 1971 and there the Association held a series of library seminars which were very well attended. In both cases grants from the Council enabled a number of Asian librarians to attend.

In the years between 1956 and 1973 the Council on Library Resources has made grants amounting to more than half a million dollars for these and other activities in the international area.. By 1970, however, it had become apparent that, for a variety of reasons, the most effective way to promote international cooperation among librarians and library systems was not through support for projects to meet needs as they emerged. Although much of significance had been accomplished, it was becoming increasingly clear that more could be achieved through assumption of a leadership role by an organization

in which representatives of many countries, including the United States, participated on an equal basis. The International Federation of Library Associations was the logical vehicle.

Founded in 1927 and with consultative status in Unesco, IFLA had played an important part as the main forum for the discussion, on an international level, of library problems. But it lacked the resources to become the effective organization it could and should be, both to meet the growing expectations of the international library community and to deal from a position of strength with other groups in allied fields, principally the International Federation of Documentalists (FID) whose activities in science information parallel those of IFLA in libraries. This is essential if libraries and their users' needs are not to be submerged by the more vocal and financially well-endowed science information groups.

The Council therefore concluded that the most useful long-term contribution it could make to international cooperation among libraries would be to assist IFLA in developing its potential for professional leadership. This decision came at a time when IFLA itself, after a period of self-examination, had determined that its influence would be greatly increased if it revised its dues schedule to afford it sufficient funds to maintain a capable permanent staff which could effectively carry forward the ongoing activities of the organization. A substantial grant from the Council, to be paid over a three-year period, has enabled IFLA to achieve this objective in the transitional years until the new dues schedule becomes fully implemented. Even then IFLA may not be able to support the secretariat and expanded new program through dues alone. Unlike FID, it receives no support from governments. The organization has some hard thinking to do if it is to achieve a firm financial base.

Among the activities sponsored by IFLA which have been brought to a satisfactory conclusion with the help of the Council is the international standardization of library statistics. A series of meetings, culminating in a meeting of a Special Committee of Governmental Experts convened by Unesco in 1970 and attended by 73 delegates from 43 countries, resulted in a document which was presented to and accepted by the General Conference of Unesco. In the words of the IFLA group: "If, as we believe, more progress has been made in getting international agreement in this field in the last two years than in the previous thirty-five, no little of the credit must go to the Council [on Library Resources] for its ... support."

The Council's concern for international cooperation has been further demonstrated by its support of the first and second U.S. - Japan Conferences on Libraries and Information Science in Higher Education, in Japan in 1969 and in the United States in 1972. It also provided funds for seven eminent American librarians to participate in the International Seminar on University Libraries arranged in Uppsala, Sweden, in 1971 in connection with the three hundred and fiftieth anniversary of the founding of that University. The Council has on several other occasions, when funds were not otherwise available, made travel grants to U.S. and Canadian librarians with leadership roles to play at international meetings abroad. For example, one of the Council's early grants, made in 1957, enabled Mr. Quincy Mumford, the Librarian of Congress, to attend the Unesco Symposium on National Libraries in Europe held in Vienna in that year. The Council also contributed toward the support of the American Library Association's International Relations Office when it was transferred from Chicago to Washington.

In the course of the past five years the Council has been fortunate in having the assistance, in this area of its activities, of perhaps the two most widely respected and important librarians of the time. Sir Frank Francis, former director of the British Museum and president of IFLA from 1964 to 1969, upon his retirement from the Museum joined the Council staff as full-time resident consultant on international library matters and served on this basis for two years. Although he returned to England in late 1970, he continues to provide assistance with regard to specific projects as well as more general matters of international import and to spend several weeks in the Council's office two or three times a year. On May 1, 1973, Dr. Herman Liebaers, current president of the International Federation of Library Associations and on leave from his position as director of the Royal Library of Belgium, came to the Council for a one-year assignment. During this period he will work with CLR to advance international cooperation and to develop programs for the benefit of library systems in the less advantaged parts of the world. In this connection, it would not be inaccurate to say that the assistance of men of their caliber, wisdom, and breadth of experience would not be available to an organization of lesser stature and respect than the Council enjoys.

We at the Council on Library Resources feel that the role the Council has played -- as catalyst, diplomat, initiator in international library cooperation -- has had an important impact on developments in this field. As an independent organization, with no ties to government and no identification with any constituency other than that created by its mission of serving the best interests of libraries everywhere, the Council has made a unique contribution to filling the needs of scholars and other library users over the world.

if given the opportunity, might find the field challenging and otherwise rewarding. The entrance of personnel with such background should also beneficially affect the attitudes and standards of the profession.

In time, the Council would hope also to initiate and support fellowship and/or internship programs to train librarians in managerial skills and in the application of advanced technology, particularly of computers, to libraries. Activities like these will lead to a broadening of opportunities within the profession, thus making it far more attractive than it at present is, both to those contemplating a choice of career and those already engaged in it.

IN CONCLUSION

The preceding pages are intended to provide a kind of guide to the Council's principal areas of activity over the years. Lengthy as it is, the paper necessarily omits a good deal. For example, little has been said about the Council's assistance to archives and archivists, and nothing about the help that has been given to government libraries through the Federal Library Committee. These and some other hard-to-classify activities might have been included in a section labeled Miscellaneous, but in view of the fact that the Committee will have available to it all CLR files and annual reports it was decided to sacrifice all-inclusiveness in favor of relative conciseness.

A caveat: This paper has been prepared by members of the Council's staff, and, although every effort has been made to avoid overstatement and self-praise, it undoubtedly reflects the dedication of professionals to an important task and to the organization that performs it.